

Original Research

Factors Influencing Employees' Commitment to Quality Improvement Practices among Manufacturing Enterprises in Tanzania

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Abstract

Employee commitment to quality improvement initiatives has been postulated as a critical driver sustainable quality improvement across business firms. While determinants of this commitment have been studied globally, little is known of such drivers for the Tanzanian manufacturing sector. Using a mixed-methods cross-sectional design, data were collected from 408 employees across 22 firms and analysed through descriptive statistics, correlations, multiple regression, and thematic analysis. Results showed that employee commitment to quality improvement was moderate. Multiple regression analysis revealed that management support, employee empowerment, communication and training significantly and positively predict the commitment of employees to quality improvement. Recognition and rewards, despite being emotionally valued by employees, did not exhibit influence mainly because it had been not consistently implemented. Qualitative results reinforced the role of leadership, trust, empowerment, timely feedback, and adequate resources in shaping commitment. The study concludes that employee commitments hinge on how management supports and engages employees. It is, therefore, imperative that Tanzanian manufacturing enterprises emphasise on managerial support, employee involvement, communication and hands-on practical training in order to develop a strong quality culture. Manufacturing firms should equip frontline staff with hands-on training on tools like 5S, root-cause analysis, basic statistical process control, and mistake-proofing to build competence and confidence. Additionally, where possible, firms should strategically integrate these ground level improvement practices to ISO 9001 processes so as to institutionalise gains and foster quality.

Keywords: Employee Commitment, manufacturing enterprises, quality improvement.

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Introduction

Manufacturing firms globally are exposed to great pressure of enhancing the quality of their products, services and processes because of competition and ever-changing customer preferences and expectations (Sinkamba *et al.*, 2024). Quality improvement (QI) measures have become a must for companies to cope with these challenges and attain higher level of customer satisfaction. QI is an ongoing pursuit of standardisation, variation reduction and defect elimination to realise increased efficiency, reliability, and performance (Karunarathna *et al.*, 2025). In practice, QI involves identification of areas for improvement, development of improvement ideas, implementation of changes, and monitoring of outcomes to achieve the desired results. Such iterative way of working is in line with methodologies that have been widely adopted in manufacturing in order to develop incremental improvements in productivity and quality. These methodologies include Lean, Six Sigma, Total Quality Management (TQM), and Kaizen (Chauhan, 2020).

QI has been more and more recognised as a strategic catalyst for driving competitiveness, efficiency, market penetrations, and customer satisfaction in manufacturing industry worldwide. For instance, the philosophy of continuous improvement was a key reason why Japan came to dominate manufacturing in the late 20th century (Cole & Yakushiji, 2020). Japanese auto manufacturers obtained far lower rates of defects than their competitors, in part by relentlessly pursuing quality through techniques like TQM and Kaizen. This qualitative advantage was important in their ability to gain entry and market share in various parts of the world during the 1980s (Cole & Yakushiji, 2020). While quality management focuses on improving product quality and minimizing error, manufacturing companies can meet new customer needs while enhancing compliance in meeting the prevailing international standards of reliability, waste reduction all over its operational systems.

In Africa, and in East Africa, there has been increasingly recognition of the role that quality continuous improvement practices can play in the manufacturing sector. Enhancing quality has become a notable agenda for the East African Community (EAC), as it seeks to make manufacturing industries competitive (Lawrence & Mupa, 2024; Guliev & Mehari, 2023). Lean strategies such Just-in-Time (JIT), Value Stream Mapping (VSM), and Kaizen have been identified as a potential solution for the manufacturing challenges and delivery of quality in general quality (Lawrence & Mupa, 2024). Manufacturing firms across East Africa are compelled to undertake such measures in response to rising intra-regional competition and evolving consumer demands.

In Tanzania, the manufacturing sector contributes approximately 8.4% GDP and provides employment to approximately 250,000 people (Santos *et al.*, 2023) as indicated by World Bank (2021). The Tanzanian government has implemented various strategic initiatives aiming at fostering industrial growth and competitiveness. One major step in this process is the establishment of special economic zones (SEZs) as the centres for industrial activity in the country. These are areas where manufacturers can enjoy financial benefits and were created with an intention to accelerate the investment made by companies. National plans like the Tanzania Five-Year Development Plan and the National Development Vision 2025 also prescribe specific goals in terms of industrial

growth, job creation and export upliftment. They emphasise growth of the manufacturing base with greater productivity and value-added industries. Government's pursuit of its industrialisation policy is centred around facilitation of development of a strong manufacturing base through investment in infrastructure and improving the business environment.

Though such initiatives address the macro-level enablers of industrial growth, sustained enhancement in quality of product and process requires a set of organisational QI practices. The focus on quality is not only about construction of physical facilities, acquisition of machinery, adoption of new technologies, and system configuration, but it's also a question of nurturing an organisation culture that values quality (Chauhan, 2020). QI initiatives span all levels of an enterprise, including top management, middle management, and shop floor personnel (Chauhan, 2020). Top management has a major role in establishing quality objective, resourcing, and team to provide quality leadership. But, successful QI largely relies on the participation and commitment of people at all levels in an organisation, because they're the ones who make changes happen, hear about problems on the ground and then create sustaining improvements (Chauhan, 2020). According to Ogu (2024) establishing a quality culture cannot be achieved by policies down there, rather employees' buy-in and active involvement will serve as the focus of motivation towards quality results. In this study, employee commitment is defined as the extent of attachment, identification, and involvement shown by an employee towards their organization's efforts to improve quality. Strong employee commitment means that workers will put in more effort to ensure high quality, that they strive for continual improvement of the work process and support of quality initiatives.

In practice, fostering high employee QI commitment is challenging. Scholars have observed that getting employees to wholeheartedly embrace continuous improvement initiatives can be difficult and requires sustained effort (Staniškienė *et al.*, 2018). There are often many competing demands on employees, and if QI tasks are seen as an added burden without clear personal or organisational benefit, commitment may wane. Moreover, without proper support such as training or empowerment, employees might feel disengaged from such programs. On the other hand, when employees feel empowered, valued, and supported, their commitment and enthusiasm for QI tend to increase (Luis Mendes, 2012).

A number of empirical studies in varying settings have documented factors relating to the organisation that impact on employee commitment to QI. In India, research found that the level of management support, adequate training in quality initiatives and employee empowerment to make decisions on quality issues, alongside the use of rewards were imperative in achieving greater employee QI commitment (Minh & Quyen, 2022). Likewise, in the study conducted by Barua (2021) in Bangladesh identified directive leadership, empowering organizational culture and employee involvement in decision-making as essential factors of employee commitment to QI.

In the context of Tanzania, there has been limited research specifically examining the drivers of employee commitment to QI in manufacturing enterprises. Many Tanzanian firms are still in early stages of adopting formal QI programs, and the extent to which their employees are committed to these practices, and what influences that commitment

is not well understood. Some indications from related studies suggest that Tanzanian manufacturers face hurdles such as limited resources, lack of awareness or expertise in quality methodologies, and sometimes insufficient commitment from top management (Matindiko & Bulemo, 2025). Customer-focused research has shown that product quality and timely delivery are among the most important determinants of customer satisfaction in the Tanzanian manufacturing sector (Mganga, 2013). This implies that companies must prioritize QI practices to satisfy customers and remain competitive. However, without understanding the human factors, specifically how to engage and commit employees to these quality practices, even well-intentioned quality initiatives may fail to yield sustainable results.

In light of the above, this study examines employees' commitment to QI practices in Tanzanian manufacturing enterprises and the factors that influence it. The main objective is to generate insights that can help firms and policymakers enhance the effectiveness of QI initiatives through better employee engagement. Specifically, the study aims to determine the level of employee commitment to QI practices in manufacturing enterprises in Tanzania. Additionally, it examines the key factors that influence employee commitment to QI practices in Tanzanian manufacturing firms.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework for this study came from Social Exchange Theory (SET) by George Homans in 1958. Social behaviour is a function of exchange that describes that people evaluate what they get in return for the work and choose to engage in activities deemed as rewarding (Homans, 1958). Therefore, employees are more likely to invest their time and loyalty in the organisation, if they are feeling recognised, supported and treated fairly (Turk & Krastev, 2022).

In the SET framework and applying it in the context of QI practices, it can be said that employees would then be more likely to have commitment toward QI practices if they sense their organization is highly supportive. Likewise, if staff are rewarded for promoting a quality service over time they will tend to sustain or increase their commitment--since the exchange has paid off. Lam *et al.* (2015) established that when employees believe their organization's procedures and decisions are fair, it strengthens their commitment to QI initiatives. From a social exchange perspective, fair treatment engenders loyalty and effort in return. Moreover, employees' perception of organizational support including being involved in decision processes is positively linked to their commitment to quality management practices (Astuty & Udin, 2020).

SET has been used to examine quality management behaviours in different contexts. For instance, Sivalogathan and Hashim (2014) examined the interplay between perceived organisational support and commitment to QI practices and revealed that the employees who perceive support from their firm are more likely to involve themselves in QI. Ahmad Zawawi *et al.* (2024) also revealed that fair treatment in how quality programmes are implemented is necessary in order to enhance employee commitment to QI. In the case of Tanzanian manufacturing firms, SET offers an interesting perspective to explore what these determinants might be like.

Empirical Literature Review and Hypothesis Development

The employee's commitment to QI practices has been studied across many industries and contexts, yielding insights into various drivers. Generally, the empirical evidence indicates that employee commitment to QI is not random and is a result of management support, employee involvement, effective communication, training and education, and recognition of employees. This section presents the proven factors that drive employees to own quality even when no one is watching.

Management commitment and support

Strong top management commitment is repeatedly mentioned as a core antecedent for nurturing a highly committed workforce. Leaders lead the way through visible commitment to quality, investment in resources, and clear goals and values for quality (Algethami *et al.*, 2025; Karim *et al.*, 2025). The more that employees believe their upper management is truly committed to continuous improvement, the greater sense of obligation they feel (Ababneh, 2020). This is supported by a number of studies where senior management commitment to QI resulted in employees more likely to enact quality goals (Bin Abdullah *et al.*, 2009). For example, a qualitative study in the Saudi manufacturing industry showed that visible leadership commitment and inconsistent direction from top leaders were key cultural enablers of QI practices (Algethami *et al.*, 2025). This is consistent with previous TQM models and international standards (e.g. ISO 9001:2015) that place leadership as a cornerstone of quality-oriented culture (Navarro & Naranjo, 2025).

Recent evidence from a study conducted in Colombia's manufacturing sector confirms that leadership and management commitment are key quality culture ingredients that result in an increase of the company's performance (Gallego & Gutiérrez, 2017). Likewise, in health care, research on patient safety and QI projects revealed that strong management support is associated with higher staff participation in improvement and longer-term success of QI teams (Gagnon *et al.*, 2024). In the context of Tanzania, empirical evidence is scarce but supportive data exists. For instance, Tandika (2024) studied public service organizations and found that the performance management practices contributed to employees perceiving value and support from management. This in turn resulted in higher employee commitment to organisational goals. This implies that when employees perceive genuine support from management, their commitment to organizational initiatives increases. Therefore, study hypothesised that:

H₁: Management support positively and significantly influences employee commitment to QI practices among manufacturing enterprises in Tanzania.

Employee involvement and empowerment

Current quality paradigms emphasise that improvements are most successful when they utilize the involvement of employees. Recent studies highlight that active participation of employees in problem-solving teams, decision-making and idea generation is an indicator for commitment to continuous improvement (Algethami *et al.*, 2025; Ogu, 2024). By engaging employees as partners in the QI process, instead of just

needing to complete tasks, they acquire ownership in results and a sense of accountability for quality results. According to Urban (2024), cultural dimensions such as employee orientation and openness result as important factors driving successful Lean implementation, something also ubiquitous observed in a wide-reaching 2021 review of Lean management situation in Europe. In the same line, a study of 255 Malaysian electronics firms revealed that employee involvement is the critical driver of employee commitment to QI practices and makes significant QIs (Bin Abdullah *et al.*, 2009). Navarro and Naranjo (2025), in a structural equation model of quality culture in manufacturing, identified employee involvement as a key construct for driving quality cultures.

What's crucial to note is that employee engagement isn't just about participating; it's also about empowering and ownership. By creating the opportunity for staff to learn from one thing, teach them how to spot problems and suggest fixes over and over again, they are more likely to be "all in" (Kiwia & Kavishe, 2024). Karim *et al.* (2025) conducted a QI analysis, which revealed that accepting and applying employees' suggestions foster a sense of empowerment and quality practices. Engagement breeds commitment as employees enjoy the pride of being associated with an organization committed to quality. A culture in organization which allows participation and team work increases the level of employee inclination towards QI (Algethami *et al.*, 2025). It is therefore hypothesised that:

H₂: Employee involvement in quality initiatives positively and significantly influences employee commitment to QI practices among manufacturing enterprises in Tanzania.

Training and education

There is general acknowledgment that employee ability and willingness to adopt QI are substantially promoted through training and education. Employees who do not know how to improve will struggle against even the best intentions. The recent literature strongly supports the idea of training as a driver of continuous-improvement culture. Empowering employees through training equips them with the technical abilities and ability to think about problems that are necessary for recognizing improvement opportunities, and implementing solutions (Algethami *et al.*, 2025; Karim *et al.*, 2025). A study conducted by Karim *et al.*, (2025) affirms training as a critical driver of a continuous improvement culture.

In the context of manufacturing enterprises in Tanzania, Matindana and Shoshiwa (2025) observed that training was a key process factor for successful Lean implementation as well as communication. According to their structural model, Lean training and education in food and beverage SMEs contributed significantly in waste reduction and increased output. The study revealed that employees who were trained in quality tools and concepts such as problem-solving techniques, 5S, statistical process control, and Six Sigma, were more effective in improvement efforts. Training inculcates "quality-first" thinking, and makes employees more confidence to take ownership of quality (Karim *et al.*, 2025). Similarly, a study of Australian manufacturers revealed that providing training on problem-solving enhances employee contributions to QI (Karim *et al.*, 2025). This leads to the hypothesis that:

H₃: Training and education positively and significantly influence employee commitment to QI practices among manufacturing enterprises in Tanzania.

Communication

Communication, especially open, transparent and two-way communication is a further crucial aspect determining commitment to QI. It often requires cultural transformation and interdisciplinary teamwork, which is only possible when there is open sharing of information and a shared understanding throughout the organization that quality goals are to be pursued. Algethami *et al.* (2025) found that communication serves as the glue of a Lean culture among Saudi manufacturers as it allows the free flow of ideas and collaborative problem-solving crucial to continuous improvement. For many companies, communication breaks down with siloed departments, no feedback loop, or one-way top-down information that keeps workers on the front lines in the dark. These barriers can have a chilling effect on commitment. When an organization fails to inform employees about quality objectives or progress, personnel may become disengaged or sceptical of efforts. However, in presence of robust communication, suggestion systems with feedback, inter-departmental knowledge sharing, organisations create an environment of trust and shared purpose that fuels commitment to QI (Algethami *et al.*, 2025; Karim *et al.*, 2025).

In Tanzania, Matindana and Shoshiwa (2025) observed in their study on Lean implementation among SMEs that when it comes to waste reduction, communication alongside training are crucial. They assert that transparent communication about process changes fosters employee engagement in lean practices. The quality management literature indicates that effective communication provides alignment, so that everyone knows the quality priorities and fosters a culture of team work in problem-solving, which strengthen employees' commitment to making QI a continuous pursuit. This leads to the hypothesis that:

H₄: Effective communication within the organization positive and significantly influences employee commitment to QI among manufacturing enterprises in Tanzania.

Recognition and rewards

Numerous studies of TQM and human motivation indicate that recognition and rewards can strengthen commitment. The logic behind this belief is that when you recognize and reward employees for quality, it reinforces behaviours that organisation truly values. Conversely, if there is no reward for going the extra mile to improve quality, employees' energy can fade over time. Bin Abdullah *et al.* (2009), in a Malaysian firms' study found significant positive effect of reward and recognition on QI commitment among employees. Similarly, recognition was explicitly highlighted as an enabler of continuous improvement among manufacturing firms in Saudi (Algethami *et al.*, 2025). This can be through formal awards (providing employees with a certificate, award, bonus payment or promotion for quality achievements) or informally by expressing appreciation (in praising meddlers praise operators/ teams which have made improvement in meddle activity).

The Australian manufacturing investigation of (Algethami et al. (2025) offers a concrete example. It found that recognition and implementation of employee suggestions can have a significantly positive effect on empowerment and reports on quality practices and performance. When employees are able to witness their idea not just be listened to but acted upon and credited, the effect is cyclical. As they feel valued, so are more likely to redouble their efforts toward quality goals within the organization. Recognition also is grounded on basic motivation theories (Herzberg's motivators, Maslow's esteem needs. The manufacturing study of by Algethami *et al.* (2025) offers a concrete example. It found that recognition enhances employees' self-efficacy, which leads to better QI. And when employees can see that their idea has been not only heard, but implemented, they feel more invested and are more likely to stay involved in QI.

It should be noted that a reward is not necessarily money. But academics warn that recognition must be fair and connected to genuine quality results. When they're done right, reward and recognition systems help forage a culture of appreciation that fuels continuous improvement. Recognition, in other words, answers that question "What's in it for me?". This energizes employees to participate in the organization's initiatives (Karim *et al.*, 2025). It was hypothesised in this study that:

H₅: Recognition and rewards for quality-focused contributions positively and significantly influence employee commitment to QI among manufacturing enterprises in Tanzania.

Conceptual Framework and Contextual Research Gap

Despite the global proliferation of QI research, there remains a notable gap in recent empirical studies focusing on employee commitment to QI in the Tanzanian manufacturing sector. Most of what we know about the factors highlighted in the literature comes from studies in industrialized economies or emerging markets in Asia, the Middle East, and to some extent other African countries. This represents both a conceptual and contextual gap that the present study aims to address.

Conceptually, the lack of local research means it is not well-established how (or if) the dynamics observed elsewhere hold in Tanzanian manufacturing firms. Globally and regionally, the five predictors are well-supported: for example, studies from developing countries have examined lean manufacturing and TQM implementations, finding that success hinges on management commitment, worker training, communication, etc. (Matindana & Shoshiwa, 2025). However, Tanzania's specific cultural, economic, and organizational context may moderate these relationships. The manufacturing sector in Tanzania is growing and faces competitive pressures (contributing ~5.6% to GDP and aiming to expand under initiatives like the Sustainable Industrial Development Plan) (Matindana & Shoshiwa, 2025). Yet, recent research on QI in this sector is very limited. One of the few studies by Matindana and Shoshiwa (2025), looked at lean manufacturing in Tanzanian SMEs and largely focused on the technical adoption of lean tools rather than on human factors like commitment. A recent systematic literature review on lean in developing countries explicitly highlighted a "general gap in lean manufacturing research in developing countries". Thus, research on the people side of quality programs, such as commitment, motivation, and cultural factors is even more sparse in these settings.

Contextually, it is possible that Tanzania's organizational culture and workforce could have unique qualities such as higher power distance, collectivist orientation, and limited resources, the implications of which might be felt with regards to how management support or rewards are perceived by subordinated staff. The absence of empirical evidence results in reliance on global findings that may not adequately address local contexts. This study intends to address this contextual gap.

Figure 1 is an illustration of how each individual independent variable is hypothesized to affect employee commitment to QI through direct paths. Each arrow indicates a presumed positive relationships according social exchange principles and previous study findings. The framework conceptualises that increased levels of management support, employee involvement, training, communication, and recognition and rewards result in greater employee commitment to QI practices.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework for Employee Commitment to QI

Research Methods

Research Design

The research was cross-sectional and employed a mixed-methods approach. Mixed method was employed to take advantage of quantitative coverage and qualitative depth (Lund, 2012). The quantitative data gave more general patterns and population testing to validate hypotheses. In contrast, the qualitative data provided a more in-depth understanding of employees' views and experiences. By this hybrid mix of tools, the study could triangulate conclusions and enrich results' interpretation. The cross-sectional design meant that data were all collected at one time. This is a non-experimental,

descriptive-correlational research that investigated the relationship between independent and dependent variables as they coexist. Causal inferences are constrained by the cross-sectional design, however, inclusion of qualitative components helped to suggest possible causal mechanisms and contextual factors underpinning the observed relationships.

Population and Sample

The study population comprised workers in manufacturing establishments in the different sub-sectors, including food and beverages, textiles, plastics and rubber products, chemicals, materials handling equipment as well as metal products. The population frame was constructed based on data provided by the Tanzania National Bureau of Statistics and industry associations to select companies located in major industrial areas (Dar es Salaam, Arusha, Mwanza, Morogoro). Sampling was conducted using a multistage process. This approach was twofold. In a first step, a purposive sampling of manufacturing companies as well as their diversity in size and sub-sector. Companies were categorized according to company size as small (<50 employees), medium (50–99) and large (100+). A sample of firms was selected from each stratum, and 22 firms finally participated (5 large-sized enterprises, 8 middle-sized and 9 small-sized), thus covering a wide range of the organisations size distribution. In the second phase, employees were recruited using simple random sampling from each selected firm. Employed as a staff member list was established, under the cooperation of management in which respondents were randomly selected for the survey. A balance of managerial, supervisory, and frontline workers from each firm was emphasized since levels of commitment to QI may differ by job description.

Given the large population of manufacturing workers and the study's aim for generalisability, a Cochran's formula was used to determine the sample size. The Cochran formula is a widely used means of determining sample size in survey research when the target population is adequately large or unknown (Bartlett II *et al.*, 2001). It permits the researcher to indicate the level of precision desired (margin of error), confidence level, and proportion in the population believed to have the attribute being measured. The formula is expressed as:

$$n_0 = \frac{Z^2 p (1 - p)}{e^2},$$

where n_0 is the initial sample size estimate (for an essentially infinite population), Z is the Z-value corresponding to the chosen confidence level, p is the estimated proportion of the population having the attribute, and e is the desired margin of error (precision level). In this study, the confidence level at 95% was set, corresponding to $Z \approx 1.96$ and the margin of error at $\pm 5\%$.

Because the true proportion p of employees committed to QI was not known a priori, the conservative estimate of $p = 0.5$ (50%) was used. This is a standard practice in sample size determination, as $p = 0.5$ maximizes the product $p(1-p)$ and thus yields the maximum required sample size for a given confidence and precision (Bartlett II *et al.*, 2001). Substituting the parameters into Cochran's formula, an initial sample size (n_0) was obtained as follows:

$$n_0 = \frac{(1.96)^2 \times 0.5 \times 0.5}{(0.05)^2} = \frac{3.8416 \times 0.25}{0.0025} \approx 384.16.$$

This calculation indicates that a sample of about 384 respondents would be the minimum required to achieve 95% confidence and $\pm 5\%$ precision under the given assumptions. In practical terms, researchers often round up such results and consider additional respondents to account for potential non-responses or unusable questionnaires. To compensate for potential non-responses or incomplete surveys, the target sample was slightly inflated to 450.

Data Collection, Measurement Instruments and Constructs

Data were collected using a semi-structured self-administered questionnaire consisting of both closed-ended and open-ended items. The survey instrument was developed in line with the research objectives and was informed by prior literature on quality management “soft factors” and employee commitment. In particular, past studies have identified management support, employee involvement, training/education, communication, and recognition/rewards as critical enablers of QI success. Table 1 summarizes each construct measured, the number of survey items (Likert-scale statements) used to assess it, and the original scholarly source from which the scale or items were derived.

Table 1: Summary of constructs and measurement items

Construct	Number of Items	Source of Scale
Management Support	4	(Minh & Quyen, 2022)
Employee Involvement	4	(Staniškienė <i>et al.</i> , 2018)
Training and Education	3	(Greebler & Surez, 1989)
Effective Communication	3	(Minh & Quyen, 2022)
Recognition and Rewards	3	(Jackson, 2004)
Employee Commitment to QI	5	(Jackson, 2004)

The selection of measurement scales was guided by their established use in quality management research. Greebler and Surez (1989) developed foundational training and education constructs for quality management that remain widely referenced in TQM literature. The items were adapted and validated through pilot testing and exploratory factor analysis (EFA) in this study to ensure contextual relevance for Tanzanian manufacturing enterprises.

A five-point Likert scale (1 = "Strongly Disagree" to 5 = "Strongly Agree") was selected for its balance between measurement sensitivity and respondent ease-of-use, which is particularly important in manufacturing settings where respondents may have varying levels of survey experience. Most of the items were measured on a five-point Likert-type scale and a minority of open-ended questions also served to collect qualitative data. Employee commitment to QI, the dependent variable, was assessed using a multi-item scale developed by Jackson (2004).

Jackson (2004) developed a dedicated employee commitment to quality scale, one of the few purpose-built instruments for measuring this construct. Its applicability to the Tanzanian context was confirmed through reliability analysis (Cronbach's $\alpha \geq 0.76$ for all scales) and EFA, where all items loaded strongly on their intended factors. In this case, employee commitment was conceptualised as unidimensional construct. Data collection was conducted over a four-week period. Consent was sought from participating organisations in advance, and questionnaires were distributed using paper-based format. Participation was voluntary, based on an informed consent, including anonymised answers for participants.

Scale Validation and Common Method Bias Assessment

Content validity was ensured through two steps. First, measurement items were drawn from established scales in the quality management literature (Table 1). Second, the instrument was reviewed by three academic experts in quality management and industrial engineering. Construct validity was assessed through EFA, with results confirming convergent validity (all items loading ≥ 0.71 on their intended factors) and discriminant validity (no cross-loading above 0.30 on any other factor). It is acknowledged that Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was not conducted, which is recommended for future research to further establish construct validity. To assess common method bias (CMB), Harman's single-factor test was conducted. An unrotated principal component analysis of all survey items revealed that the first factor accounted for 28.3% of the total variance, well below the 50% threshold (Podsakoff et al., 2003). This indicates that CMB does not pose a serious threat to the validity of the findings.

Data Analysis Methods

Data were analysed through a mixed-method approach. Quantitative data were analysed with descriptive statistics, correlations, multiple regressions to examine employees' level of commitment and factors affecting it. Descriptive statistics (means, SDs and frequency distributions) were used to examine commitment levels, whereas Pearson correlations model, as well as the regression models examined the respective contributions of independent variables. Linearity, normality, homoscedasticity and multicollinearity assumptions were checked and satisfied before performing the regression. Subgroup comparisons (t-tests and ANOVA) were also performed to examine relationships between role, certification status, and tenure with commitment.

Qualitative data from open-ended questions were analysed thematically following Braun and Clarke's six-step approach. The analysis involved: (1) familiarisation with the data through repeated reading of all open-ended responses; (2) systematic open coding where initial codes were generated independently by two coders; (3) collating codes into potential themes; (4) reviewing themes against the coded extracts and the entire dataset; (5) defining and naming final themes; and (6) producing the report with illustrative quotes. Inter-coder agreement was 85%, and discrepancies were resolved through discussion until consensus was reached. Integration of qualitative and quantitative findings followed a convergent design, whereby qualitative themes were systematically mapped against each quantitative predictor to confirm, enrich, or explain the statistical results.

Results and Discussion

Respondent demographic profile

A total of 408 completed questionnaires were gathered and statistically analysed, indicating response rate of approximately 90.7%. Demographic characteristics of the respondents are summarised in Table 2. 60% of the respondents were male, in line with the dominance of males within the manufacturing sector. At the organizational level, participants were of various ranks 5% senior manager, 15% middle managers, 20% supervisors and 60% operational staff. Participants were selected in various company sizes, with around 20% coming from small companies (fewer than 50 employees), and 37% coming from medium ones (...between 50 and 99...), whereas the remaining represented big companies (100 or more). It is interesting to note that only 5 of the 22 companies (about 23%), were ISO certificated (including most of large and medium firms) and they provided nearly a quarter of corporate members. This is pertinent as companies certified to ISO are generally assumed to have more established quality management procedures.

Table 2: Respondent Demographic Profile of Participants (N = 408)

Characteristic	Category	N	%
Gender	Male	245	60.0%
	Female	163	40.0%
Job Role	Senior Management	20	4.9%
	Middle Management	61	15.0%
	Supervisor	82	20.1%
	Operational Staff	245	60.0%
Tenure	< 1 year	40	9.8%
	1–5 years	164	40.2%
	6–10 years	122	29.9%
	> 10 years	82	20.1%
Firm Size	Small (<50 employees)	80	19.6%
	Medium (50–99 employees)	152	37.3%
	Large (100+ employees)	176	43.1%

According to the demographic profile both leadership and staff were represented. The overrepresentation of the sample from operational level employees (60%) was an advantage for the study, because most of the employees involved in production were included. The inclusion of managers indicates their commitment to quality.

Reliability of measurement scales

Reliability of each multi-item scale was tested before hypothesis testing. Internal consistency for all scales was acceptable, since all Cronbach's α coefficients were above the 0.70 cut-off, as shown in Table 3. Employee QI commitment showed a $\alpha = 0.86$ level of reliability, which can be considered as reasonable. The best reliability among the predictors was found for management support ($\alpha = 0.90$), indicating very stable response patterns about the commitment of leadership to quality.

Table 3: Scale Reliability (Cronbach's α) for Study Variables

Scale	Number of Items	Cronbach's α
Commitment to QI	5	0.86
Management Support for QI	4	0.90
Employee Involvement in QI	4	0.85
Training & Education for QI	3	0.82
Communication about Quality	3	0.80
Recognition & Rewards for Quality	3	0.76

Note. QI = QI. All α values ≥ 0.76 , indicating satisfactory internal consistency.

Reliability was also high for employee involvement ($\alpha = 0.85$) and training and education for quality ($\alpha = 0.82$). The communication scale ($\alpha = 0.80$) and recognition and rewards for quality efforts ($\alpha = 0.76$) met reliability criteria. The α values provide evidence that the measurement questions for each construct were internally consistent. The results of the reliability estimates provide evidence that each of the scales was measuring a distinct factor with minimal random error.

Exploratory factor analysis

An exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was performed to reveal the embedded structure for factors associated with QI commitment. By using principal components extraction with varimax rotation, five factors were identified (eigenvalues > 1), corresponding to expected groups of items. The rotated factor loadings of each item are indicated in Table 4 and organized by factor.

Table 4: Exploratory Factor Analysis: Rotated Factor Loadings for Questionnaire Items

Factor / Item	Loading
Factor 1: Management Support	
Top management emphasizes continuous QI (MS1)	0.80
Leadership allocates sufficient resources for QI (MS2)	0.78
Management regularly reviews quality performance (MS3)	0.75
Factor 2: Employee Involvement	
Employees are encouraged to suggest QIs (EI1)	0.77
Teams regularly discuss quality issues (EI2)	0.73

Factor / Item	Loading
Employees are involved in quality-related decision-making (EI3)	0.71
Factor 3: Training & Education	
Employees receive training in QI practices (TR1)	0.82
New employees receive quality orientation (TR2)	0.78
Regular workshops on quality tools are provided (TR3)	0.75
Factor 4: Communication	
Quality goals are clearly communicated to employees (CM1)	0.79
Feedback on quality performance is provided in a timely manner (CM2)	0.76
Employees understand how QI aligns with company objectives (CM3)	0.74
Factor 5: Recognition & Rewards	
Good QI work is formally recognized (RR1)	0.80
Employees are rewarded for QI efforts (RR2)	0.77
QI achievements are publicly acknowledged (RR3)	0.72

The factors explained about 67% of the variance in the dataset showing a large amount of shared variance by the extracted factors. Only factor loadings greater than or equal to 0.70 are reported for coherence). All items loaded strongly on their intended factors (loadings 0.71–0.82) and showed minimal cross-loading (no secondary loading above 0.30 on any other factor), supporting the convergent and discriminant validity of the measures. These results confirm that the survey instrument successfully differentiated the key dimensions hypothesized to influence employee commitment to QI.

Assumption checks for regression analysis

Statistical assumptions were checked before conducting regression models as shown in Table 5. The context of the residuals on the criterion variable was almost normal, slightly skewed (0.15) with a slight kurtosis (−0.45). Hence, they were all well within acceptable values (± 1), which means that there were no serious deviations from normality. A Kolmogorov–Smirnov test for residuals was not significant ($p > 0.05$), indicating that normal distribution was acceptable. Linearity was supported by the look of scatterplots of residuals versus fits, which showed no systematic non-linearity in the relation between each predictor and outcome.

Homoscedasticity (constant error variance) was confirmed using a Breusch–Pagan test (χ^2 statistic non-significant, $p = 0.27$). Visual inspection of residual scatter plots indicated that residuals were evenly distributed across the range of predicted values with no funnel-shaped spread indicating variances for errors approximately equivalent at all expected levels of the criterion variable. No issue was observed during the multicollinearity diagnostics as moderate inter-correlations among predictors and high tolerance had been reported. All VIFs ranged from 1.2 to 2.3 (much less than the typical threshold of 5.0) indicating that independent variables were highly discriminative, but did not overlap too much. Additionally, the independence of errors assumption was checked with the Durbin–Watson statistic ($DW = 1.99$), which is very close to 2.0, indicating no autocorrelation in residuals. In sum, these diagnostics suggest that the data satisfy the assumptions required for valid multiple regression inference.

Table 5: Assumption Checks for Multiple Regression

Assumption	Check/Indicator	Result
Normality	Skewness = 0.15; Kurtosis = -0.45 (residuals)	Approx. normal (within ± 1 range)
Linearity	Residuals vs. predicted plot	Linear pattern (no curvature)
Homoscedasticity	Breusch-Pagan test, $p = 0.27$	Met (constant error variance)
Multicollinearity	VIF range = 1.2 – 2.3	Low multicollinearity (VIF < 5)

Note. Durbin-Watson statistic = 1.99 (independence of errors satisfied). No major assumption violations detected for regression analysis.

Descriptive statistics

Table 6 provides the descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) for all key variables. The general employee level of commitment to QI was moderate ($M = 3.40$; $SD = 0.65$; 5-point scale). As such, it suggests that employees were not very committed, but also not uncommitted to participating in QI initiatives. Thus, employees' allegiance has room to increase. Regarding the independent variables, management support had a mean of 3.50 ($SD = 0.70$), indicating that employees on average slightly agreed with their top management's support toward quality initiatives. Employee involvement in quality decision had a mean (SD) of 3.20 (0.75), showing that employees did not feel they had fair opportunities for involvement-just above neutral.

Table 6: Descriptive Statistics for Key Variables (1–5 Likert Scale)

Variable	Mean	SD
Commitment to QI	3.40	0.65
Management Support for QI	3.50	0.70
Employee Involvement in QI	3.20	0.75
Training & Education for QI	3.05	0.80
Communication about QI	3.30	0.68
Recognition & Rewards for QI	2.90	0.72

Training and education for quality had a mean of 3.05 ($SD = 0.80$), suggesting that training for QI is minimally offered in many companies. Communication of quality goals and feedback was rated at 3.30 ($SD = 0.68$), indicating relatively moderate amount of clear communication of less than 'strong' in all organisation. Recognition and rewards for QI was the poorest scoring factor (mean = 2.90, $SD = 0.72$) and rated below the neutral midpoint of 3.0. This indicates that many staff reported good QI was not recognised or rewarded every time. It is worth mentioning that the higher standard deviations (0.7–0.8) of some variables such as training or recognition mean there was great variation in the experiences among respondents. In general, these descriptive results indicate that the element of management support is what is perceived in the most positive manner compared to the dimension of formal recognition for quality were not, which can also be considered as related to human resource motivation.

Correlation analysis

The Pearson correlations of all the main variables are shown in Table 7. Cross-correlations exhibited significant direct positive associations as expected. Employee engagement in QI was negatively and significantly related to all five factors (all $p < 0.01$). In this respect, commitment and management Support ($r = 0.50$) as well as commitment and employee involvement ($r = 0.45$) had high significant positive correlations with each other. This suggests that among enterprises in which management support for QI is perceived to be relatively strong and employees are actively engaged, people have higher levels of commitment to quality practices. Additionally, communication ($r = 0.42$), training and education ($r = 0.40$) and recognition and reward ($r = 0.30$) were positively correlated to commitment, but the correlation between recognition and commitment was weaker than that of other factors in this dimension. All these relationships were significant at the 0.01 level, indicating that the better an organization provides any one of these supportive factors, the higher employee commitment it will have.

Many of the inter-correlations between independent variables were moderate to strong. This is consistent with an industry in which these quality characteristics frequently are observed together. For example, management support was positively related to employee involvement ($r = 0.60$) and communication ($r = 0.55$), such that in organizations where top management is committed, they are also more likely to involve employees, and communicate quality aims with greater clarity respectively. Employee involvement was also highly associated with communication ($r = 0.50$). Training was moderately related to other factors ($r = 0.40$ – 0.50 range), such as $r = 0.50$ with management support indicating that management who supports the work invests in training staff for QI. Recognition and rewards while positive, resulted to be significantly less related to the other constructs ($r = 0.33$ with communication; $r \approx 0.30$ with involvement and commitment support). This could suggest that the formal recognition programs are somehow separated and considering that there might be organizations with strong leadership and involvement practices, which in anyway does not have a robust recognition for quality efforts.

Table 7: Correlation Matrix for Study Variables

	Commitment	Mgmt. Support	Involvement	Training	Communication	Recognition
Commitment (QI)	—					
Management Support	0.50**	—				
Employee Involvement	0.45**	0.60**	—			
Training & Education	0.40**	0.50**	0.40**	—		
Communication	0.42**	0.55**	0.50**	0.45**	—	
Recognition & Rewards	0.30**	0.35**	0.25**	0.18*	0.33**	—

Note. N = 408. $p < 0.01$ for correlations $\geq .18$; $p < 0.05$ for $r \approx 0.12$ – 0.17 (two-tailed). QI = QI. All shown correlations are positive.

The correlation results provide preliminary support for all the hypothesized relationships, as each factor is positively associated with commitment to QI. The strongest bivariate association is between management support and commitment ($r = 0.50$), underlining how crucial visible leadership commitment is for employees' own

commitment levels. The substantial correlation between involvement and commitment ($r = 0.45$) also aligns with theory that involving employees in decisions breeds ownership and commitment. However, because many predictor variables are intercorrelated (for example, management support and involvement at $r = 0.60$), it is necessary to examine their unique contributions through multivariate regression. The moderate inter-correlations also raised the importance of the multicollinearity check discussed earlier (Table 5), which fortunately indicated these relationships are not problematic for regression. In the next section, we turn to the multiple regression results to identify which factors have significant independent effects on employee commitment when considered together.

Multiple regression results

A multiple linear regression analysis was performed to determine the extent to which the five factors (management support, employee involvement, training, communication, and recognition) predict employee commitment to QI practices. The overall regression model was significant, $F(5, 402) = 55.3, p < 0.001$ showing that the predictors reliably account for variance in employee commitment. The R^2 of the model was 0.45, indicating that 45% of variance in commitment to QI is explained together by these five factors. This is a large effect size for behavioural studies, indicating that these factors are collectively quite meaningful predictors of how committed employees are to QI.

The regression coefficients are given in Table 8. Management support was revealed to be the best unique predictor of commitment ($\beta = 0.30, p < 0.001$). Employee involvement was also a strong independent predictor ($\beta = 0.25, p < 0.001$). Communication regarding quality objectives and performance was also significantly positive ($\beta = 0.20, p < 0.001$). Training and education were also associated with higher QI commitment ($\beta = 0.15, p = 0.017$). Notably, recognition and rewards for QI did not show a significant unique effect on commitment ($\beta = 0.05, p = 0.19$).

Although recognition was positively correlated with commitment bivariate ($r = 0.30$), once the other factors are controlled, its unique influence appears negligible. This non-significant finding suggests that formal recognition, as currently implemented in these firms, is not a differentiating factor in predicting which employees are more committed to quality. It may be that recognition programs are scarce or inconsistently applied (as the low mean of 2.90 hinted), and thus many employees have not experienced meaningful rewards for quality contribution – limiting its impact. Another interpretation is that recognition overlaps substantially with general management support; employees might perceive managerial encouragement and support as implicit recognition, so when that is accounted for, explicit recognition programs add little extra value.

As a robustness note, multicollinearity does not appear to distort these results, as the VIF values for all predictors remained low (Table 8), confirming that each coefficient is estimating a unique piece of variance. The Durbin–Watson statistic (~ 1.99) also indicated independence of residuals, as mentioned earlier.

Table 8: Multiple Regression Predicting Employee Commitment to QI

Predictor	B	SE B	β	t	p	VIF
Constant	0.58	0.20	—	2.9	0.004	—
Management Support	0.28	0.04	0.30	7.5	<0.001	2.1
Employee Involvement	0.22	0.04	0.25	5.5	<0.001	2.3
Training & Education	0.12	0.05	0.15	2.4	0.017	1.4
Communication	0.19	0.04	0.20	4.8	<0.001	1.9
Recognition & Rewards	0.05	0.04	0.05	1.3	0.190	1.3
Model F (5, 402)	55.3				<0.001	
R ² (Adj. R ²)	0.45 (0.44)					DW = 1.99

Results from the regression analyses indicate what is important when everything else is considered simultaneously. The organisation's management support for QI seems to be the most important, with a relatively strong standardised impact on employee commitment. This is consistent with the current literature's focus on leadership in quality management. Workers even in Tanzanian manufacturing appear to be responding in kind, as they are able. The second important factor is employee engagement. Irrespective of the form of, and potentially irrespective of whether or not there is, generalized support from management: to give employees a voice and a role in QI-related decision-making will lead to increased level of commitment on their part, one would assume by stimulating ownership and intrinsic motivation with respect to quality. Communicating well about quality is also believed to be very influential. This demonstrates that the presence of communication channel helps workers who know what to do and are part of the process, to enhance their commitment toward improvement. On the other hand, lack of signature recognition effect is informative. It might be possible that reward and reinforcement prototypes generated from the prototypical firm will not result in commitment, or perhaps employees value practical support and participation over verbal feedback. Recognition can also influence commitment indirectly by reinforcing perceptions of support; however, when support is explicitly modelled the effect of recognition is weaker.

In sum, management visibly encouraging QI, involving staff, and communicating clearly while also providing training will cumulatively foster much greater employee commitment to quality practices. All of the hypotheses are supported, except formal recognition by itself did not appear as a distinctive incentive along with other factors. The next section discusses whether there were variations in the level of commitment among different employee and firm certification status groups, followed by a general discussion regarding these results with respect to theory and prior studies.

Subgroup analyses

To enhance the understanding, further tests were conducted among categories of employees considering one's job and if a company is certified according to ISO 9001. The purpose was to determine whether specific types of workers or organizations reveal considerably stronger/weaker commitment, which could guide interventions.

Commitment by job role

Employee commitment levels were also measured among the four job designations (senior management, middle management, supervisors and operational staff). Details of the summary statistics are presented in Table 9. There were variations in commitment means with respect to hierarchy levels. QI commitment was the highest among senior managers (mean = 3.80, SD = 0.50) and second highest among middle managers (mean = 3.60, SD = 0.55).

Supervisors reported a medium commitment (Mean = 3.40, SD = 0.60) at the same level as the entire sample on average. Operation staff was the least attached to the organization (mean = 3.30, SD = 0.62). One way between group ANOVA revealed a significant difference among these role groups in commitment ($F(3, 404) = 6.21, p < 0.001$). Post-hoc comparisons (Tukey's HSD) further showed that senior managers were significantly more committed than operational staff ($p < 0.01$), and middle managers also had higher commitment than operational staff ($p < 0.05$). The difference between senior management and middle management was not statistically significant ($p = 0.30$), nor was the difference between supervisors and operational staff ($p = 0.20$) after adjustments for multiple comparisons were made.

Table 9: Employee Commitment to QI by Job Role

Job Role	N	Mean Commitment	SD
Senior Management	20	3.80	0.50
Middle Management	61	3.60	0.55
Supervisor	82	3.40	0.60
Operational Staff	245	3.30	0.62

These findings indicate that managers, particularly higher-level managers, are more committed to QI programmes than front-line staff. This finding is, perhaps, not surprising as senior managers are frequently the instigators of quality initiatives and may feel a degree of ownership or accountability for their effectiveness. Especially because they are closer to strategic goals, middle managers also have increased commitment. Conversely, operating staff (who make the majority of employees in the hospital) demonstrate the lowest levels of dedication, perhaps because they feel that they have limited impact on decision-making or viewing QI as imposed rather than self-initiated behaviour. The supervisor group mean (3.40) fell in between, not significantly different from staff in this sample, which might indicate that line supervisors in these firms share many of the same constraints or outlooks as non-supervisory staff when it comes to quality practices. The gap between management and staff commitment aligns with the idea that those who set and enforce policies (management) are more invested in them than those who must implement changes on the ground. It points to a potential need to better engage and motivate operational employees, for instance through greater empowerment or by showing them the benefits of QI in their daily work.

Commitment by ISO 9001 certification status

Employee commitment levels between those working in ISO 9001 certified firms (5 firms, $n \approx 100$ employees) and those in non-certified firms (17 firms, $n \approx 308$ employees) were compared. The ISO 9001 standard requires formal quality management system by documenting and tracking quality management practices. A significant difference was found in the results. Workers from ISO-certified companies reported on average-greater commitment (mean ≈ 3.40 , $SD = 0.65$) than those from non-certified companies (mean ≈ 3.20 , $SD = 0.72$). This difference was significant, $t(406) = 2.89$, $p = 0.004$. It seems that the formal quality management systems and practices according to ISO 9001 certification can lead to the improvement of quality culture which may contribute in a minor respect toward enhancing employee commitment. In an organization certified to ISO, the QI might be more integrated with regular work (e.g., via standard operating procedures, audits, continuous improvement programmes), and this norm might also more so become internalized by employees. On the contrary, non-certified firms are expected to have less formalised production practices in place for quality and this results in a lesser base of commitment from employees. However, it was observed that even in ISO-certified firms the commitment was only moderate (3.40 on a 5-point scale), highlighting that certification alone does not guarantee employee commitment.

Table 10: Commitment to QI by ISO Certification Status

Firm ISO 9001 Status	N	Mean	SD
ISO-Certified Firms	200	3.40	0.65
Not ISO-Certified	208	3.20	0.72

Overall, the findings portray a moderate level of commitment to QI among staff with significant impact being exerted by some organisational variables. Management support, employee involvement, communication, and training had distinct positive effects on commitment, while recognition did not have a direct ability to predict commitment when the other factors were included. Substantial variation across sub-groups was also evident with managers and those working in ISO-certified environments having higher levels of commitment than non-managers and those working outside of an ISO-certified environment. These quantitative results are then explicated with the help of qualitative observations and theoretical lenses to gain a more comprehensive understanding of employees' commitment towards QI in the Tanzanian industrial setting.

Qualitative Insights from Open-Ended Responses

In addition to the quantitative data collected, respondents provided open-ended responses on what motivates and discourages their participation in QI. A thematic analysis of these qualitative responses revealed several related themes to survey results. Some of the significant themes were leadership role model and trust. One of the production workers accepted, "You know, it's easy to talk about quality but it really is important to 'walk the talk'." "We determine that we want the quality when our managers are actually, really trying to achieve it," said one. These thoughts were congruent with the quantitative result that management support is the most significant, and they highlight how workers appreciate leaders who overtly value quality and promote trust.

Another theme was empowerment and taking control. Several non-managers mentioned legitimating them to make decisions which supported their efforts to hold themselves singularly responsible for the quality of the outcomes. *“I feel more responsible for the quality of outcomes when I have latitude to adjust processes.”* These views are focusing on the foundation of ownership, rooted in having employees with ‘skin in the game’, or those that want to have a sense of autonomy and tackle problems themselves versus waiting for bureaucracy to respond. This parallels the regression output in which both empowerment and involvement showed large effects.

Communication was also recognized critical. The prompt information received on quality performance and the open declaration of goals were largely viewed as drivers. *“As a frontline staff, I feel more engaged when management shares quality metrics results with us and involves us in problem solving;”* one respondent explained. Poor communication or no voice was, in contrast, reported as a barrier. One other employee said: *“There are times where decisions get made about processes and it doesn’t involve us, and it just is demoralizing.”* These narratives underscored the importance of upward and downward communication in enhancing commitment.

Lack of resources was also widely referred to. In accordance with the quantitative results, employees complained about old devices, lack of staff and lack of time for development projects. A quality inspector said, *“We have some ideas how we can improve but we’re already very much on the limit at the line; there is no room for improvement activities.”* These narratives reflect how even the most optimistic and committed respondents can become lethargic if their own turn out not to have the resources or opportunities, emphasising the importance of resource exchange for sustaining commitment.

While recognition did not make it in the regression, qualitative data emphasized its emotional effect. Some respondents noted that even small gestures of gratitude boosted morale. For example, one respondent commented, *“Just a simple ‘Good job’ from my boss when I discover and repair a bug really helps. It makes me want to do more.”* Others lamented the dearth of acknowledgment, with one commenting, *“We only hear about mistakes, never about improvements.”* Comments like these indicate that in this interpersonal level, acknowledging people, though sporadically done, is still a powerful motivator.

Other factors mentioned by employees were quality culture and peer influence. For respondents in the ISO-certified companies, a strong “quality culture” was established where conformance to standards were both required and reinforced. *“It’s just how we do things here;”* one employee said. In contrast, in non-certified firms, respondents noted that such culture did not exist, saying *“People don’t take improvement seriously because it’s not enforced or rewarded.”* These findings suggest that a collective value and social norms-based quality culture environment can have the potential to exert considerable influence on individual commitment, echoing social exchange reciprocity arguments of mutual expectations.

The qualitative impressions, taken together, help to substantiate the quantitative findings. They provide insight into the influence of management support, empowerment,

communication, recognition, resources and culture on employee commitment to QI practices. Of note, recognition was not found as a statistically significant predictor in the regression outcome analysis, but the results from the qualitative data suggest that it should not be considered on equal footing with other indicators. As the results suggest, leadership engagement, trust, open communication, appreciation and appropriate resources do influence employees' willingness to go the 'extra mile' for QI.

Conclusion

This study concludes that employee commitment to QI practices is not happen unconditionally. It is cultivated through reciprocal exchanges. It hinges on how management supports and engages employees. Thus, investing in visible management support, employee empowerment, open communication, and practical training will enhance employee commitment to QI practices. While ISO 9001 certification can provide useful guidelines, it cannot replace the daily actions of managers that make quality a real part of employees' work. The key task for managers is therefore to make these supportive practices routine, especially at the frontline, so that QI becomes a normal part of organizational life rather than just a temporary initiative.

Theoretical Implications

The study's findings provide strong support for the SET perspective, as well as extending its applicability to the manufacturing quality domain in a growing economy. Applying the SET framework, management support, employee involvement, communication and training can be interpreted as organisational investments or benefits that demonstrate to employees that the organisation values their contributions and well-being. If employees see that top management is wholeheartedly behind quality in the form of visible commitment, resource allocation and/or quality leadership then they will feel bound to offer higher levels of commitment to QI practices.

The study has revealed employee involvement as a form for 'participatory' exchange relations at the organisation level. The organisation shows trust and respect by giving employees decision-making power and hands-on roles in the QI process, and employees reciprocate with role ownership and accountability. Communication is the informational life-blood of the mutual relationship however; clear, frequent presenting of quality and performance goals and results keeps the exchange flowing-providing employees with information about what's going on and why. Training is a developmental transaction; what the organisation invests in to support and develop staff capability development, they can expect (with time) to return in form of increased ability and willingness to use new skills in QI.

Importantly, the non-significant result for recognition and rewards provides a crucial theoretical contribution. A SET perspective would suggest that recognition, in the form of direct reciprocity for quality behaving, provides increased commitment. Nevertheless, the qualitative material demonstrates that recognition in the studied companies was of an ad hoc, unpredictable nature which also tended to be negative by the identification of shortcomings rather than by appreciating improvements. In terms of the SET, this represents a "broken exchange signal"; employees cannot reliably count on recognition in response to their excellent efforts, so it doesn't serve as an effective component in the exchanges. The relatively low mean level of recognition also suggests this reading. This

suggests that, in order for recognition to act as a valid medium of exchange within SET it must be stable and fair, and have clear connections with objectively measured quality behaviours – attributes which were largely absent within the sampled companies. The use of SET to understand both significant and nonsignificant findings is a contribution to the theoretical literature on employee QI commitment.

Practical Implications

The findings suggest that visible leadership support, active employee involvement in improvement activities problem solving process, two-way open communication as well as providing and demonstrating practical repetitive training can strengthen commitment to QI among the manufacturing employees. More specifically, the key implications for Tanzanian manufacturing managers from the unique findings of this study include (a) engaging in daily 15-minute quality huddles led by supervisors to examine quality metrics, provide feedback, and engage frontline staff in problem-solving. This explicitly accounts for the strong effects of trust in management, communication and involvement. (2) Because operational staff have less commitment to continuous improvement efforts than managers, firms should direct their empowerment initiatives at the frontline by forming quality circles or small improvement teams that allow operational employees to own and lead specific QI projects. (3) Provide hands-on training for front line staff in the use of practical QI tools, such as 5S workplace organisation, root cause analysis (e.g., 5 whys, fishbone diagrams), basic statistical process control and mistake proofing (poka-yoke) to develop both competence and confidence. (4) Following the low recognition perception, managers should consider introducing simple and instantaneous public praise systems for promoting certain QI behaviours before implementing more complex reward schemes. (5) Firms should, where appropriate, strategically link these shop-floor improvement practices to their ISO 9001 processes (e.g., internal-audits, follow-up on corrective action plans, management review) in order to institutionalise gains and embed quality into everyday operations.

Recommendations

In order to create a strong quality-oriented culture and holistically enhance competitiveness, organizations in the manufacturing industry companies need to emphasize visible management support, genuine employee empowerment and open channels of communication on feedback and problem-solving frameworks. Frontline-led QI should be institutionalized to enhance employee involvement. One way to accomplish this is by providing practical hands-on training in 5S, basic SPC, root-cause analysis and mistake-proofing. Additionally, to the extent possible, companies should coalesce these grassroots drives for improvement with ISO 9001 processes (e.g., internal audits, corrective action follow-up, management review) so that gains become rooted in the organization and quality becomes sustainable without excessive red tape.

Limitations and Areas for Further Study

This study had several limitations that may restrict the interpretation of results. First, the cross-sectional nature prevents any causal inference; although management support is intuitively predicted to influence commitment, only longitudinal and/or experimental

research can establish causality. Second, the use of self-report measures implies the risk of common method bias, although Harman's single-factor test indicated that the first factor explained only 28.3% of variance, suggesting CMB is not a serious concern. Future studies may consider supplementing Harman's test with more robust approaches such as the Common Latent Factor (CLF) technique or marker variable method. Validity may be enhanced in the future through the inclusion of objective measures, e.g., defect rates or independent assessments of management practice.

Third, the purposive sampling of firms and management-mediated provision of staff lists for random sampling may introduce selection bias. Readers should exercise caution against over-generalising these findings beyond manufacturing firms in Tanzania and other similar developing contexts. Fourth, while construct validity was supported through EFA, Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was not conducted. Future studies should employ CFA to further validate the measurement model. Finally, the qualitative interpretations were derived from open-ended survey responses that provided good contextual information but limited depth. Although two coders independently coded the data with 85% inter-coder agreement, future studies using in-depth interviews or focus groups could provide deeper understanding of, for example, experiences with recognition practices and perceptions about the extent to which management is supportive.

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